

Root diameter of IR20 and Kinandang Patong in aeroponics and field experiments.

genotypes were sampled at 33 d after emergence to determine root diameter and total root length. Roots were collected from four replications from depths of 0-0.1, 0.1-0.2, 0.2-0.3, and 0.3-0.4 m using a monolith soil sampler (0.20 × 0.20 × 0.40 m³). Roots were washed and diameter was measured for 25-50 root segments from a random sample of 10 primary axes from each layer. Total root length was measured with an optical scanner for all roots on all layers.

Root number was not associated with drought response nor with root diameter

and *d* = distal. Twenty-five segments from each of the portions were laid on a flat surface and their widths measured with a micrometer to estimate root diameter.

Roots of field-grown plants of three

(see table). Root diameter was greatest in drought-tolerant and least in susceptible lines or cultivars. Total root length under aeroponics appeared to be greater for drought-tolerant than for drought-susceptible rice genotypes, but the same was not true under field conditions.

Our observations, although confined to only a few lines and cultivars, confirm results of previous aeroponic studies on drought resistance, which also involved only a few genotypes. Root thickness is a relatively stable character; hence, there was high correlation ($r = 0.97^{**}$) between root diameter measured in aeroponic- and field-grown rice (see figure). Thus it is possible to select for root thickness under aeroponics. As the trait also appeared to be related to drought response, aeroponic evaluation of root diameter may assist in selecting drought-tolerant rice genotypes. ■

Fertilizer management—*inorganic sources*

Response to P of some rice varieties in Assam, India

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We evaluated the performance of IR8, Jaya, Monoharsali, and Mahsuri at different P levels.

The soil is acidic with pH 5.5 (1:2 glass electrode method), sandy loam texture, 0.6% N (Kjeldahl method), 7 kg P/ha (Brays and Kurtz No. 1), and 65 kg K/ha (neutral ammonium acetate

method). We applied 0, 8.8, 17.6, and 26 kg P/ha basally as single superphosphate, 40 kg N/ha as urea, and 17 kg K/ha as muriate of potash. The experiment was laid out in a factorial randomized complete block design with three replications. We used the Vanado molybdate method to measure P uptake by plants at maturity.

Monoharsali yielded the most grain (Table 1). Grain yield of all varieties significantly increased as P increased.

Mahsuri was tallest with 26 kg P/ha, and IR8 had the heaviest roots. P uptake

was greatest at 26 kg P/ha; it decreased as P decreased (Table 2).

P fertilizer-use efficiencies were 24.0, 21.8, and 18.8 kg grain/kg P applied at 8.8, 17.6, and 26 kg/ha. P-uptake efficiency decreased as fertilization increased. This might be due to the equilibrium effect of 40 kg N/ha and 17 kg K/ha. The correlation between grain yield and P uptake was highly significant ($r = 0.85^{**}$), indicating that P uptake influenced yield. ■

Table 1. Interaction of variety and P level on yield of some rice varieties in Assam, India.

P level (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)				
	IR8	Jaya	Monoharsali	Mahsuri	Mean
0	2.6	2.7	3.1	3.0	2.9
8.8	3.0	3.1	3.8	3.5	3.3
17.6	3.3	3.4	4.1	4.0	3.7
26	3.4	3.7	4.3	4.5	4.0
Mean	3.1	3.2	3.8	3.8	—
LSD (0.05)	V = 0.1	P = 0.1	V × P = 0.45		

Table 2. Effect of P on several characters of some rice varieties. Assam, India.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Root weight (g/m ²)	P uptake (kg/ha)
<i>Variety</i>			
IR8	91.99	180.80	36.99
Jaya	100.04	113.53	44.62
Monoharsali	111.13	114.65	48.35
Mahsuri	112.73	117.37	49.53
LSD (0.05)	0.83	4.31	0.84
<i>P level (kg/ha)</i>			
0	100.29	84.76	32.16
8.8	101.55	104.27	43.90
17.6	105.08	129.93	48.29
26	108.96	135.38	55.13
LSD (0.05)	0.86	4.31	0.84